

New and little-known Seguenziidae (Vetigastropoda, Gastropoda) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain

Especies nuevas y poco conocidas de Seguenziidae (Vetigastropoda, Gastropoda) de la cadena de montañas submarinas del sur de las Azores

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ABSTRACT

Six species belonging to the family Seguenziidae collected on the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC) have been studied. Three species are described as new: *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp., *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp., and *Asthelys hyeresensis* n. sp. The distributions of these new taxa are probably restricted to the bathyal crests and slopes of the SASC. *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp. is part of a regional radiation within the genus where three NE Atlantic species show a large morphological similarity. In contrast, *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp. is very dissimilar to the NE Atlantic *Carenzia carinata* (Jeffreys, 1877). The genus *Asthelys* is represented by two morphologically different species.

RESUMEN

Se han estudiado seis especies pertenecientes a la familia Seguenziidae, recolectadas en la cadena de montañas submarinas del sur de las Azores (SASC). Tres especies se describen como nuevas: *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp., *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp., y *Asthelys hyeresensis* n. sp. La distribución de estos nuevos taxones probablemente esté restringida a las crestas y taludes batiales de la SASC. *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp. es parte de una radiación regional dentro del género donde tres especies del Atlántico nororiental muestran una gran similitud morfológica. En contraste, *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp. es muy diferente a la especie del Atlántico noreste *Carenzia carinata* (Jeffreys, 1877). El género *Asthelys* está representado por dos especies morfológicamente distintas.

INTRODUCTION

This paper reviews the Seguenziidae encountered in sediment samples gathered during the cruises SEAMOUNT-2 (GOFAS 1993), POS397 (GEORGE 2010) and M151 (FRANK 2018) to the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC). Locations visited included Atlantis Seamount, Tyro

Seamount, Plato Seamount, Irving Seamount, Hyères Seamount, Great Meteor Seamount and Little Meteor Seamount (see Figs. 1-2). One objective of these cruises was to study the biodiversity of the plateaus and slopes of the seamounts in the SASC.

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Figure 1. Map with the location of the study area in the NE Atlantic Ocean. Bathymetry data GEBCO, depth contour 1000 m.

Figura 1. Mapa con la ubicación del área de estudio en el noreste del Océano Atlántico. Datos de batimetría GEBCO, isobatas 1000 m.

The main historical works on the Gastropoda of this area are focused on the Azores and include WATSON (1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889), DAUTZENBERG & DE BOURY (1896), and DAUTZENBERG & H. FISCHER (1896, 1897a, 1897b). Several molluscan taxa occurring on the bathyal slopes and crests of the SASC and Lusitanian Seamounts were reviewed recently following the SEAMOUNT-1 and -2 cruises: Pyramidellidae (PEÑAS & ROLÁN 1999), Fasciolaridae (GOFAS 2000), Muricidae (HOUART 2001), *Trituba* Jousseaume, 1884 in Newtoniellidae (GOFAS 2002), Tonnoidea (GOFAS & BEU 2002), *Clelandella* Winckworth, 1932 in Trochidae (GOFAS 2004), Pectinoidea (DIJKSTRA & GOFAS 2004), Bivalvia (KRYLOVA 2006), Coralliophilinae (OLIVERIO & GOFAS 2006), Rissooidea (GOFAS 2007), Lasaeidae (GOFAS & SALAS 2008), and *Haloceras* Dall, 1889 (GOFAS 2018).

Important historical records on NE Atlantic species in Seguenziidae include

WATSON (1879, 1886), and JEFFREYS (1876, 1877 and 1885). WATSON (1879) reported on two genera and 11 species found during the “Challenger” expedition. JEFFREYS (1876, 1877 and 1885) introduced one new genus and three species obtained during the “Valorous”, “Lightning” and “Porcupine” cruises.

More recently, QUINN (1983a, 1983b, 1987 and 1991) reviewed the superfamily Seguenzioidea and introduced four new genera and a set of new species. Marshall reviewed the taxa from New Zealand (MARSHALL 1983), the Tasman, South Pacific and Southern Antilles Basins (MARSHALL 1988), and New Caledonia and Loyalty Islands (MARSHALL, 1991). Marshall introduced nine new genera and many new species from the southern Pacific Ocean. POPPE, TAGARO & DEKKER (2004) introduced one new genus and many new taxa from the Philippine Islands. GEIGER (2017, 2019) studied

Figure 2. Map of SASC. Distribution of *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp. is indicated by red dots, *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp. by yellow triangles and *Asthelys hyeresensis* n. sp. by a green diamond. Bathymetry data GEBCO, depth contours 1000 m.

Figure 2. Mapa de SASC. Distribución de *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp. indicada por puntos rojos, *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp. por triángulos amarillos y *Asthelys hyeresensis* n. sp. por un rombo verde. Datos de batimetría GEBCO, isobatas 1000 m.

seguenziids from the NE Pacific and introduced three new species. In the Atlantic basin, HOFFMAN, VAN HEUGTEN & LAVALLEYE (2011) reported on a few seguenziid species from the Rockall and Hatton Banks off Ireland. LIMA, CHRISTOFFERSEN & BARROS (2013) studied the genus *Ancistrobasis* and LIMA, CHRISTOFFERSEN

& VILLACAMPA (2014) the genus *Basilissopsis* from off Brazil. SALVADOR, CAVALLARI & SIMONE (2014) reviewed the seguenziids from off SE Brazil with the description of two new species. HOFFMAN & FREIWALD (2017) reported on two new species from the Coral Patch Seamount off NW Morocco.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area (Figs. 1-2). The SASC are submerged seamounts of volcanic origin, located 500 – 1000 km south of the Azores (Fig. 1). Atlantis Seamount (34.1 °N – 30.2 °W) is a rugged volcanic structure of 75 x 150 km with several edifices and a flattened summital plateau at a depth of about 300 m. The surrounding seafloor is at about 3500 m. Plato Seamount (33.2 °N – 29.6 °W) is a narrow East – West ridge of about 30 x 150 km with two main peaks culminating at about 650 m. The gap with Atlantis is about 60 km and reaches a depth of 3000 m. Tyro Seamount (34.0 °N – 28.3 °W) is a small (20 x 40 km) seamount in the NE of the SASC. It has a flattened top at about 350 m and the surrounding seafloor reaches 3200 m. Irving Seamount (33.0 °N – 28.0 °W) is a large structure with a large summital plateau at about 250 m. The distance between Irving and Plato is about 100 km and the corresponding channel has a depth of some 3200 m. Hyères Seamount (31.4 °N – 28.9 °W) is a rugged structure with a large raised area of about 30 x 80 km culminating at approximately 270 m. The channel towards Irving is at some 2200 m; the distance between the main crests of Irving and Hyères is approximately 90 km. Great Meteor Seamount (30.0 °N – 28.5 °W) is a giant subsea mountain of about 100 x 80 km with a large summital plateau of 80 x 50 km at approximately 300 m depth, and the surrounding sea floor reaching 4500 m. The flat top structure as well as many rounded boulders on the flank is proof that the crest was once eroded by a surface wave front. The northern, western and southern flanks were explored by ROV dives in the M151 cruise (FRANK, 2018) and they showed predominantly volcanic outcrop with rich megafauna including remains of a large deep-water coral chain. The flat plateau was extensively sampled in the POS397 cruise (GEORGE, 2010); it is covered with fine bioclastic sediment inhabited by small-sized macrofauna. It is probable that

the megafauna (for example Porifera and Cnidaria) of the plateau were damaged by deep-sea trawling; very few megafauna were found on the plateau by POS397 despite many historic records. In contrast, the megafauna on the flanks seemed intact. Little Meteor Seamount (29.6 °N – 29.0 °W) is a small round seamount with a diameter of about 15 km, approximately 50 km SW of Great Meteor Seamount and separated by a channel at a depth of 3200 m; the crest is flattened at a depth of approximately 300 m. The sediment at the crest and the fauna and geological features of the NE Flank are similar to those of the Great Meteor Seamount.

Methodology. Sediment and biological samples were taken in 280 – 1960 m water depth by grab sample, dredge, epi-benthic sled, box core, and ROV manipulator. The sediment samples were sieved and the fractions larger than 0.5 mm were rinsed in fresh water and dried in an oven at 40°C before transport. The sediment samples were sorted with a low magnification stereo microscope (Zeiss Sterni 2000) for shells. Selected specimens were imaged using a Keyence microscope or using a Scanning Electron Microscope (VEGA3-Tescan). Finally, specimens were determined and stored in the voucher collections at SaM (Wilhelmshaven) and MNHN (Paris). Our inventory of shell-bearing molluscs from the SASC currently comprehends more than 350 species. Holotypes were deposited in the MNHN (Paris). Paratypes were stored in MNHN and in SMF (Frankfurt am Main).

Abbreviations:

Institutions: MNHN – Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle; SMF – Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt; SaM – Senckenberg am Meer.
Cruises: M151 – R/V Meteor cruise 151; R/V – research vessel; POS397 – R/V Poseidon cruise 397; SMT2 – R/V Suroit cruise SEAMOUNT-2.
Morphology: H – height; W – width, maximum diameter in apertural view.

SYSTEMATICS

MOLLUSCA, GASTROPODA, VETIGASTROPODA, SEGUENZIOIDEA Verrill, 1884

Family SEGUENZIIDAE Verrill, 1884

Six species in Seguenziidae have been found in our material from the SASC: *Basilissopsis watsoni* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896, *Basilissopsis athenae* n.sp., *Carenzia marismontis* n.sp., *Asthelys munda* (Watson, 1879), *Asthelys hyeresensis* n. sp. and *Ancistrobasis reticulata* (Philippi, 1844).

Genus *Basilissopsis* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897

Type taxon: *Basilissopsis watsoni* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897 by monotypy.

DAUTZENBERG & H. FISCHER (1897) did not provide a diagnosis of the genus which was placed in Adeorbidae. QUINN (1991) provided an extensive generic discussion based on morphological features of the type species and *Basilissopsis rhyssa* (Dall, 1827) and concluded that the genus should be placed in Seguenzioidea rather than Trochidae (but see LIMA *ET AL.*, 2014). Quinn's arguments included the nacreous sculpture and the presence of a weak labial sinus in *B. rhyssa*.

Basilissopsis watsoni Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897 (Figs. 3-11)

Basilissopsis watsoni Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897a: 40.

Basilissopsis watsoni Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897b: 163-164, pl. 3 figs. 9-11.

Material examined: Atlantis Seamount – M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab, three shells; SMT2/DW261, 34.373 °N - 30.463 °W, 1190-1340 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 72 shells; SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795-830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 20 shells. Tyro Seamount – SMT2/DW278, 33.963 °N - 28.373 °W, 890-925 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, seven shells. Hyères Seamount – SMT2/DW185, 31.425 °N - 28.863 °W, 950-1250 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, five shells; SMT2/DW200, 31.318 °N - 28.600 °W, 1060 m, 18-I-1993, dredge, 33 shells. Great Meteor Seamount – M151/23429-ROV1, 30.082 °N - 28.730 °W, 1032 m, 26-X-2018, ROV sample, two shells. Little Meteor Seamount – M151/23434R4, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 865 m, 27-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23436, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell.

Remarks: *Basilissopsis watsoni* is widely distributed on the continental slopes and on oceanic banks and seamounts in the NE Atlantic from Iceland to the Azores in 1000-1600 m (WARÉN, 1996). The shells here studied were collected in the bathymetric range 677–1340 m.

Basilissopsis athenae n. sp. (Figs. 2, 12-23)

Type material: Holotype (shell, Figs. 12-14, MNHN-IM-2000-35183), figured paratypes 1-2 (Figs. 15-18, MNHN-IM-2000-35184), 30 shells (MNHN-IM-2014-7958), 30 shells (SMF 351083), about 150 shells (SaMID 84615), all from M151/23419-2.

Other material examined: Atlantis Seamount – M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 93 shells; M151/23408, 33.996 °N - 30.177 °W, 617 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 505 shells; SMT2/DW255, 34.082 °N - 30.255 °W, 335-340 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, 77 shells, seven live-collected specimens; SMT2/DW258, 33.997 °N - 30.203 °W, 420-460 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, 195 shells, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610-655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 114

shells; SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795-830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 16 shells; SMT2/TS270, 34.080 °N - 30.249 °W, 330 m, 04-II-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW274, 34.086 °N - 30.226 °W, 280 m, 05-II-1993, dredge, two shells. Tyro Seamount – SMT2/DW277, 33.998 °N - 28.343 °W, 945-1000 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, six shells. Plato Seamount: SMT2/DW240, 33.205 °N - 29.032 °W, 565 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, five shells; SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, 2581 shells; SMT2/DW247, 33.228 °N - 29.588 °W, 580-625 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, three shells. Irving Seamount – SMT2/DW208, 32.066 °N - 27.898 °W, 785-790 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW209, 31.986 °N - 27.933 °W, 435-460 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW231, 32.025 °N - 27.908 °W, 745-750 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, 52 shells; SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, 885 shells; SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, 177 shells. Hyères Seamount – SMT2/DW182, 31.387 °N - 28.892 °W, 480 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, 279 shells; SMT2/DW185, 31.425 °N - 28.863 °W, 950-1250 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW188, 31.500 °N - 28.992 °W, 310 m, dredge, 15 shells; SMT2/DW192, 31.465 °N - 28.985 °W, 700-750 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, 6 shells; SMT2/DW203, 31.158 °N - 28.725 °W, 845-990 m, 19-I-1993, dredge, 83 shells. Great Meteor Seamount – POS397/89-5, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 316 m, 14-III-2010, Shipek grab, 15 shells; POS397/89-6, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 315 m, 14-III-2010, Shipek grab, 47 shells; POS397/89-7, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 316 m, 14-III-2010, Shipek grab, three shells; POS397/91-10, 30.083 °N - 28.633 °W, 310 m, 14-III-2010, Shipek grab, one shell; POS397/96-5, 29.950 °N - 28.633 °W, 310 m, 17-III-2010, Shipek grab, two shells; POS397/96-6, 29.950 °N - 28.633 °W, 310 m, 17-III-2010, Shipek grab, one shell; POS397/96-7, 29.950 °N - 28.633 °W, 309 m, 17-III-2010, Shipek grab, six shells; M151/23425-ROV1, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 948 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23425-ROV6, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, 115 shells; M151/23425-ROV9, 29.568 °N - 28.340 °W, 855 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, 44 shells; M151/23429-ROV8, 30.086 °N - 28.726 °W, 906 m, 26-X-2018, ROV sample, five shells; SMT2/DW143, 30.165 °N - 28.469 °W, 330 m, 10-I-1993, dredge, 136 shells; SMT2/DW148, 30.200 °N - 28.410 °W, 615 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW152, 30.033 °N - 28.368 °W, 470 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, 235 shells, SMT2/DE174, 30.040 °N - 28.710 °W, 620 m, 14-I-1993, dredge, five shells; SMT2/DW179, 30.010 °N - 28.705 °W, 570-730 m, 14-I-1993, dredge, five shells. Little Meteor Seamount – M151/23434-ROV4, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 865 m, 27-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23436, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 52 shells; M151/23437, 29.654 °N - 29.014 °W, 811 m, 27-X-2018, grab, three shells; M151/23438, 29.655 °N - 29.004 °W, 464 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 72 shells.

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, in bioclastic yellow sand with dead solitary scleractinians, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 319 m, 24-X-2018.

Etymology: Athena was the project name of the M151 cruise that visited the type locality.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 12-14): small-sized shell (H 2.0 mm, W 1.7 mm), solid, with an elevated, definitely cyrtocoenoid spire with both axial and spiral sculpture and flat base, colour cream white.

Protoconch – simple, nucleus with in total $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, with fine and irregular sculpture terminated by a narrow but definite, rounded rim, somewhat flaring, W 0.24 mm. Transition to teleoconch obvious by flaring lip and change in sculpture.

Teleoconch – Spire conical with $4\frac{3}{4}$ whorls. Initial whorls keeled. Ultimate and penultimate whorls flattened outline. Apical angle in apertural view 60°. Angle on keel between adapical and basal surface 80° in apertural view.

First whorl with approximately 30 oblique axial ribs, a keel at the edge of the narrow flat shoulder and a second keel on

the peripheral area. Ribs thickened where overrunning the keels. Fine irregular growth lines visible between ribs. Profile of first whorl below the keel nearly vertical. Second whorl with 26 axial ribs. Third whorl with 26 axial ribs, and additionally four spiral cords with blunt nodules at the intersections with the axial ribs; the first spiral cord at the shoulder, the second at the keel on the upper whorl face, the third mid-way on the steep periphery, the fourth above the suture. Fourth whorl has 30 ribs and four spiral cords; towards the lower suture a narrow concave area with a smooth spiral cord demarcating the base of the whorl. Growth lines more prosocline (about 45° with spire axis) than the axial ribs (about 30°). The remaining body whorl has a weakened sculpture and a flat sloping outline. Suture shallow. Microsculpture on whorl surface with small

Figures 3-11. *Basilissopsis watsoni* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897, Atlantis Seamount, SMT2 / DW161. 3-5: H 1.8 mm, W 2.3 mm; 6, 7: H 2.1 mm, W 2.2 mm; 8, 9: W 2.1 mm, protoconch W 0.26 mm; 10, 11: W 1.6 mm, protoconch W 0.26 mm.

Figuras 3-11. Basilissopsis watsoni Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897, Banco Atlantis, SMT2 / DW161. 3-5: 1,8 mm alto, 2,3 mm ancho; 6, 7: 2,1 mm alto, 2,2 mm ancho; 8, 9: 2,1 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,26 mm ancho; 10, 11: 1,6 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,26 mm ancho.

irregular nodular features, size of about 0.005 mm (Fig. 14).

Base of the body whorl flattened, three strong cords near the periphery, five weaker cords on the centre of the base. A ninth spiral cord demarcates the umbilical area. Umbilicus nearly closed by pallial and columellar callus. Numerous flexuous growth lines.

Aperture 35% of shell height, angular near columella and at adapical end, broadly rounded abapically. Lip

blunt at adapical end and sharp abapically, not thickened, prosocline at about 45° with spire axis, no evidence of labial sinus. A thick smooth callus covers the lip and columella, thinning out and becoming flexuous on the parietal side, internally nacreous with a broad margin at the aperture. Columella curved, callus demarcating edge to body whorl.

Variability: Some specimens exhibit a weak keel on the periphery of the body whorl yielding a more angular outline.

The body whorl may be lowered further under the penultimate whorl. Umbilicus may be completely closed or partly open. Height up to 2.3 mm.

Distribution: SASC, 29.6 – 34.5 °N, 27.5 – 30.5 °W, 280 – 1250 m.

Remarks: Placement in *Basilissopsis* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897 is based on the morphological similarity with *Basilissopsis vanheugteni* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017 and *Basilissopsis watsoni* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897. The sculpture on the basis, the protoconch and the microsculpture are nearly identical. The outline and teleoconch sculpture varies (1) from an open umbilicus in *B. watsoni* to a nearly-closed umbilicus in *B. athenae* n.sp., (2) a stepped flattened teleoconch outline in *B. watsoni* to a raised conical outline, (3) from a strong cord with basal disk to a weak one, (4) from fine oblique axial ribs to coarser ribs.

QUINN (1991) used the nacreous sculpture of the spire and the presence of a weak labial sinus of *Basilissopsis rhyssa* (Dall, 1927) as arguments for placement of the genus in Seguenzioidea, but he considered the type material of *B. watsoni* too poorly preserved to reach a similar conclusion regarding the type taxon *B. watsoni*. However, fresher specimens of *B. watsoni*, *B. vanheugteni* and *B. athenae* show a micro-sculpture and no sign of a nacreous external layer. We compared our NE Atlantic specimen with the lectotype of *B. rhyssa* designated by LIMA ET AL. (2014: fig. 3 A-D) from off Fernan-

dina, Florida ('Albatross', sta. 2668, 30°58' 30" N, 79°38' 30" W, 538 m). *Basilissopsis rhyssa* lacks microsculpture, has a nacreous appearance and a labial sinus that is absent in the NE Atlantic species. These features indicate that *B. rhyssa* probably belongs to a different taxonomic group.

A significant number of shells from *B. athenae* were predated; round holes with concave drill features with a diameter of about 0.3 mm were found (Figs. 15-16) at the base of the body whorl some $\frac{1}{2}$ - $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls from the lip in a position where a retracted animal cannot escape predation. Often, these types of drill holes are made by naticids, or muricids (BROMLEY 1981). Some cephalopods make oval holes; Octopoda drill minute holes to inject venom; nematodes make much smaller holes (BROMLEY 1981; WISSHAK ET AL. 2015). We assume that muricids are the culprits because naticids have been hardly found in our samples; we found six muricids that are potential predators: *Dermomurex gofasi* Houart, 1996, *Trophonopsis droueti* Dautzenberg, 1889, *Trophonopsis muricatus* (Montagu, 1803), *Timbellus atlantideus* (Bouchet & Warén, 1985), *Actinotrophon actinophorus* (Dall, 1889), and *Orania fusulus* (Brocchi, 1814).

The live-collected specimens and shells were found in fine to coarse bioclastic sand with remains of Porifera, Scleractinia, Octocorallia, Hydrozoa, Bryozoa, and Mollusca. The slopes of the seamounts were populated by live specimens of these groups.

Genus *Carenzia* Quinn, 1983

Type taxon: *Seguenzia carinata* Jeffreys, 1877 by original designation.

QUINN (1983a) provided a diagnosis for the genus, which includes a wide variety of morphotypes. The type taxon has convex whorls with one strong keel at the periphery and a weak keel on the upper whorl face; the remaining sculpture is nearly smooth both above and below the periphery; umbilicus is widely open. MARSHALL (1991) pro-

vides an example of variability in the genus with *Carenzia acanthodes* Marshall, 1991, where a strong spiral sculpture is developed on the base of the whorl and a flexuous finer axial as well as spiral sculpture above the periphery. We take into account this variability to place in this genus our species here described.

Figures 12-23. *Basilissopsis athenae* n. sp. 12-18. Great Meteor Seamount, M151 / 23419-2. 12-14: holotype, H 2.0 mm, W 1.7 mm; 15, 16: paratype H 2.0 mm, W 1.7 mm; 17, 18: paratype W 1.4 mm, protoconch W 0.24 mm. 19-23: Atlantis Seamount, SMT2 / DW255. 19, 20: H 1.8 mm, W 1.7 mm; 21-23: H 1.8 mm, W 1.8 mm.

Figuras 12-23. Basilissopsis athenae n. sp. 12-18. Gran Banco Meteor, M151 / 23419-2. 12-14: holotipo, 2,0 mm alto, 1,7 mm ancho; 15, 16: paratipo 2,0 mm alto, 1,7 mm ancho; 17, 18: paratipo 1,4 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,24 mm ancho. 19-23: Banco Atlantis, SMT2 / DW255. 19, 20: 1,8 mm alto, 1,7 mm ancho; 21-23: 1,8 mm alto, 1,8 mm ancho.

Carenzia marismontis n. sp. (Figs. 2, 24-31)

Type material: Holotype (shell, Figs. 24-26, MNHN-IM-2000-35185), figured paratypes 1-3 (shells, Figs. 27-31, MNHN-IM-2000-35186), 30 shells (MNHN-IM-2014-7959), 30 shells (SMF 351084), 105 shells (SaMID 83719), all from M151/23408, 21-X-2018, grab sample.

Other material examined: Atlantis Seamount – M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 26 shells; SMT2/DW258, 33.997 °N - 30.203 °W, 420-460 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, 65 shells, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610-655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 10 shells; SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795-830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, one shell. Plato Seamount – SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, 131 shells. Irving Seamount – SMT2/DW208, 32.066 °N - 27.898 °W, 785-790 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW209, 31.986 °N - 27.933 °W, 435-460 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, three shells; SMT2/DW225, 32.143 °N - 28.178 °W, 1030-1035 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW231, 32.025 °N - 27.908 °W, 745-750 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, four shells; SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, 232 shells; SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, 57 shells. Hyères Seamount – SMT2/DW188, 31.500 °N - 28.992 °W, 310 m, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW192, 31.465 °N - 28.985 °W, 700-750 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, three shells. Great Meteor Seamount – POS397/114-5, 29.683 °N - 28.434 °W, 288 m, Shipek grab, one shell; M151/23419-2, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 319 m, 24-X-2018, grab sample, one shell; M151/23425-ROV1, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 948 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, 9 shells; M151/23425-ROV4, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 945 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, 3 shells; M151/23425-ROV6, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, 41 shells; M151/23425-ROV9, 29.568 °N - 28.340 °W, 855 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, 91 shells; SMT2/DW143, 30.165 °N - 28.469 °W, 330 m, 10-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW152, 30.033 °N - 28.368 °W, 470 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, 11 shells; SMT2/DE174, 30.040 °N - 28.710 °W, 620 m, 14-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW179, 30.010 °N - 28.705 °W, 570-730 m, 14-I-1993, dredge, one shell. Little Meteor Seamount – M151/23434-ROV4, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 865 m, 27-X-2018, ROV sample, three shells; M151/23436, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 61 shells; M151/23437, 29.654 °N - 29.014 °W, 811 m, 27-X-2018, grab, four shells; M151/23438, 29.655 °N - 29.004 °W, 464 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 62 shells.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, in bioclastic coarse sand with dead hydrozoans and scleractinians, 33.996 °N - 30.177 °W, 617 m.

Etymology: *marismontis* refers to the habitat, in Latin: seamount.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 24-26): Small-sized shell (H 1.4 mm, W 2.3 mm), moderately solid, with a low spire, with two keels and a weak sculpture above the periphery and a smooth convex base, colour cream white.

Protoconch – simple larval shell with $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, fine irregular rough sculpture, terminated by a very narrow, rounded rim. W 0.25 mm. Transition to teleoconch obvious by change in sculpture (Figs. 28, 31).

Teleoconch – Spire flattened with five stepping whorls and flattened apex, all whorls with a keel at the edge of a broad shoulder. Suture shallow.

First whorl with approximately 28 oblique axial ribs and one spiral cord with keel at the edge of the broad flat shoulder. Ribs thickened at the intersections with the keel. Above the keel, areas smooth between the axial ribs. A set of

many horizontal striae immediately below the keel and two spiral striae above the suture. Profile below the keel concave. Second whorl with 52 flexuous axial ribs and three spiral cords. Third whorl with 64 axial ribs, four spiral cords, the first at the shoulder, and three below the keel. Micro-sculpture of tiny nodules and line segments across the lower whorl face. Fourth whorl 60 axial ribs, three spirals on the shoulder area, one spiral on the keel, four spirals below the keel. Micro-sculpture over the full whorl face. The body whorl (fifth whorl) shows the same features above the periphery.

Basal area below the strong peripheral keel convex, surrounding a broad and deep umbilicus. The surface towards the umbilical margin is smooth with fine flexuous growth lines. The umbilicus is delimited by a flat, rounded spiral cord, bordered by a spiral groove with shallowly-

Figures 24-31. *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp. Atlantis Seamount, M151 / 23408. 24-26: holotype, H 1.4 mm, W 2.3 mm; 27, 28: paratype 1, W 2.1 mm, protoconch W 0.26 mm; 29: paratype 2, H 1.3 mm, W 2.1 mm; 30, 31: paratype 3, W 1.7 mm, protoconch W 0.25 mm.

Figuras 24-31. Carenzia marismontis n. sp. Banco Atlantis, M151 / 23408. 24-26: holotipo, 1,4 mm alto, 2,3 mm ancho; 27, 28: paratipo 1, 2,1 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,26 mm ancho; 29: paratipo 2, 1,3 mm alto, 2,1 mm ancho; 30, 31: paratipo 3, 1,7 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,25 mm ancho.

etched rectangular pits. Inside of the umbilicus with one thick rounded spiral cord, followed by a smooth spiral area and a coarsely-beaded interior.

Aperture 40% of shell height, angular near columella and at adapical end, broadly rounded abapically (Figs. 24-26). Edge of lip is pointed but not sharp, not

thickened, generally prosocline, a strong labial sinus on the adapical side, a large labial protrusion above the periphery, a second smaller labial sinus at the periphery and a regressing lip at the anterior side. A thick, smooth callus covers the lip and columella, thinning out and becoming flexuous on the parietal side. Surface some-

what glossy inside and externally. Columella curved, with a distinct notch at its base. The callus at the adapical sinus forms a rib (Fig. 26) inside the aperture.

Variability: This species shows little variability. Sub-adult specimens lack the elaborate lip and only show an adapical sinus and a pointed protrusion below (Figs. 27, 30).

Distribution: SASC, 29.5 – 34.5 °N, 27.5 – 30.6 °W, 288 – 1035 m.

Remarks: Placement in a particular genus has been problematic as the species shares morphological features from several genera, for example, the smooth base from *Fluxinella* Marshall 1983, the elaborate lip from *Sequenzia* Jeffreys 1876, the aperture and base of *Carenzia*, Quinn 1983, and a sculpture reminiscent of *Ancistrobasis*, Dall 1889. However, the com-

bination of features does not fit the diagnosis of any genus. We have settled it in *Carenzia* because we consider it similar to *Carenzia acanthodes* Marshall, 1991 from New Caledonia. This species also has a wide open umbilicus and sculpture on the upper whorls but differs in having spirals on the base. The type species *Carenzia carinata* (Jeffreys, 1877) shares features with our new species; it has a strong keel at the periphery and one weak keel above it, a smooth base and a notch in the lower part of the columella. It deviates from our species by a weak sculpture on the upper whorls, and a simple straight lip. Our species is also quite similar to *Basilissopsis bassa* Lima Christoffersen & Villacampa, 2014 from off Brazil but this species does not have a notch in the columella nor the elaborate lip.

Genus *Asthelys* Quinn, 1987

Type taxon: *Basilissa munda* Watson, 1879, by original designation.

Asthelys is a morphologically narrow-defined genus with a smooth

whorl face and base and a keel at the periphery.

Asthelys munda (Watson, 1879) (Figs. 32-39)

Basilissa munda Watson, 1879: 596-597.

Asthelys munda: QUINN, 1987: 67, figs. 9-14.

Asthelys munda: HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017: 68, figs. 29-33.

Material examined: Atlantis Seamount – SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795-830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 16 shells. Tyro Seamount – SMT2/DW277, 33.998 °N - 28.343 °W, 945-1000 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, three shells; SMT2/DW278, 33.963 °N - 28.373 °W, 890-925 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, three shells. Plato Seamount – SMT2/DW250, 33.210 °N - 29.287 °W, 1450-1500 m, 01-II-1993, dredge, 369 shells. Great Meteor Seamount – M151/23425-ROV6, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell.

Distribution: Latitude range 26 – 56 °N, amphi-atlantic. Bathymetric range 504–2311 m. We found shells on the Galicia Bank, Coral Patch, Tyro, Plato and Great Meteor Seamounts and on the SW slope of Florida, all in sediment containing coral remains (QUINN, 1987; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD 2017; this study).

Remarks: The species shows morphological variability, particularly in juvenile specimens. Normally the columella is

curved and oblique but occasionally it is straight, nearly vertical with a minor spine at the base (Fig. 32). An internal channel is occasionally present at the keel. The protoconch has a thin varix (Fig. 35), but this feature is mostly eroded in adult specimens (Fig. 39). The umbilicus is occasionally nearly closed (Fig. 33) with an umbilical cord but more commonly open (Fig. 37). The base often has spiral cords but is occasionally smooth.

Figures 32-39. *Asthelys munda* (Watson, 1879). 32-35: Plato Seamount, SMT2 / DW250. 32, 33: H 2.6 mm, W 2.3 mm; 34, 35: W 2.1 mm, protoconch W 0.30 mm. 36-39: Hyères Seamount, SMT2 / DW200. 36, 37: H 3.4 mm, W 3.2 mm; 38, 39: W 2.0 mm, protoconch W 0.29 mm. *Figuras 32-39. Asthelys munda* (Watson, 1879). 32-35: Banco Plato, SMT2 / DW250. 32, 33: 2,6 mm alto, 2,3 mm ancho; 34, 35: 2,1 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,30 mm ancho. 36-39: Banco Hyères, SMT2 / DW200. 36, 37: 3,4 mm alto, 3,2 mm ancho; 38, 39: 2,0 mm ancho, protoconcha 0,29 mm ancho.

Asthelys hyeresensis n. sp. (Figs. 2, 40-45)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35187), paratype 1 (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35188) from SMT2/DW200m 18-I-1993, dredge.

Type locality: Hyères Seamount: 31.318 °N - 28.600 °W, 1060 m.

Etymology: *hyeresensis* refers to the type locality, the Hyères Seamount.

Description (based on the holotype, an empty shell, Figs. 40-41): Small shell (H 3.8 mm, W 3.1 mm), solid, with a conical spire and flattened apex, axial ribs, peripheral keel and convex base, apex angle 50°, colour white.

Protoconch – simple larval shell with $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, smooth, bordered by a flexu-

ous, sharp lip. W 0.25 mm. Transition to teleoconch obvious by change in sculpture (Fig. 44).

Teleoconch – Raised conical spire with five flattened whorls. Suture shallow.

First whorl with flattened shoulder with weak keel and 17 slightly proso-

Figures 40-45. *Asthelys hyeresensis* n. sp., Hyères Seamount, SMT2 / DW200. 40-42: holotype, H 3.8 mm, W 3.1 mm; 43-45: paratype 1, H 3.7 mm, W 3.2 mm, protoconch W 0.33 mm.

Figuras 40-45. Asthelys hyeresensis n. sp., Hyères Seamount, SMT2 / DW200. 40-42: *holotipo*, 3,8 mm alto, 3,1 mm ancho; 43-45: *paratipo* 1, 3,7 mm alto, 3,2 mm ancho, *protoconcha* 0,33 mm ancho.

cline axial ribs. Microscopic rough nodular sculpture. Second whorl with 20 axial ribs and sloping shoulder area, with weak keel and incised spiral channel immediately above the suture. Third whorl sculpture as second whorl but with a rounded, nodose spiral cord at the base bordered by a concave spiral area above. Fourth whorl with fading axial ribs, strong nodose spiral cord at the base. Fifth (body) whorl smooth with the knobs also disappearing on the peripheral cord, a concave area above keel.

Base area convex with five incised grooves; two strong ones near periphery and another strong one near umbilicus, two weak ones in between. Umbilical

area demarcated by a broad corrugated cord. Umbilicus tortuous and narrow.

Aperture 30% of shell height, trapezoidal, columella sloping, slightly curved, lip sharp, prosocline without sinus. Callos thin, inside smooth. (Figs. 40, 42).

Variability: The variability within the type material is very small.

Distribution: only known from type locality.

Remarks: Placement in *Asthelys* Quinn, 1987 is based on the raised conical outline, the convex base, the flattened apex, and the narrow umbilicus. The type species *A. munda* is more fragile and has a smooth whorl face. The genera *Carenzia* Quinn, 1983 and *Hadroconus* Quinn, 1987 have a wide open umbilicus.

Figures 46-50. *Ancistrobasis reticulata* (Philippi, 1844), Tyro Seamount, SMT2 / DW279. 46-48: H 5.5 mm, W 6.9 mm; 49, 50: W 3.6 mm, protoconch W 0.33 mm.

Figuras 46-50. Ancistrobasis reticulata (Philippi, 1844), Banco Tyro, SMT2 / DW279. 46-48: 5,5 mm alto, 6,9 mm ancho; 49, 50: 3,6 mm, protoconcha 0,33 mm ancho.

Genus *Ancistrobasis* Dall, 1889.

Type taxon: *Basilissa costulata* R. B. Watson, 1879 (type by monotypy).

Ancistrobasis reticulata (Philippi, 1844) (Figs. 46-50)

Solarium reticulatum Philippi, 1844: 149, pl. 25 fig. 6.

Ancistrobasis reticulata: HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2011: 97-98, figs. 104-105.

Material examined: Atlantis Seamount – M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 28 shells; M151/23408, 33.996 °N - 30.177 °W, 617 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 28 shells; SMT2/DW261, 34.373 °N - 30.463 °W, 1190-1340 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 12 shells; SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610-655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 17 shells; SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795-830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 19 shells. Tyro Seamount – SMT2/DW277, 33.998 °N - 28.343 °W, 945-1000 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, 33 shells; SMT2/DW278, 33.963 °N - 28.373 °W, 890-925 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, 200 shells; SMT2/DW279, 33.927 °N - 28.395 °W, 760-805 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, 40 shells. Plato Seamount – SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, one shell. Irving Seamount – SMT2/DW208, 32.066 °N - 27.898 °W, 785-790 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW221, 32.297 °N - 28.255 °W, 1160-1180 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, three shells; SMT2/DW222, 32.347 °N - 28.262 °W, 1150 m, 27-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW225, 32.143 °N - 28.178 °W, 1030-1035 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW231, 32.025 °N - 27.908 °W, 745-750 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, five shells; SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, 49 shells. Hyères Seamount – SMT2/DW186, 31.435 °N - 28.863 °W, 1520 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW200, 31.318 °N - 28.600 °W, 1060 m, 18-I-1993, dredge, 234 shells; SMT2/DW203, 31.158 °N - 28.725 °W, 845-990 m, 19-I-1993, dredge, 170 shells. Great Meteor

Seamount – M151/23425-ROV1, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 948 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23425-ROV6, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, two shells; M151/23429-ROV1, 30.087 °N - 28.727 °W, 1032 m, 26-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23429-ROV8, 30.086 °N - 28.726 °W, 906 m, 26-X-2018, ROV sample, three shells. Little Meteor Seamount – M151/23434-ROV4, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 865 m, 27-X-2018, ROV sample, four shells; M151/23436, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 27 shells; M151/23437, 29.654 °N - 29.014 °W, 811 m, 27-X-2018, grab, one shell.

Distribution: Latitude range 30 °S – 59 °N, amphi-atlantic. Depth range 27–1170 m (ROSENBERG 2009; HOFFMAN ET AL. 2011; this study).

Remarks: We compared NE Atlantic specimens with shells from the western

slope of the Bahama Bank and from the SW slope off Florida and we considered them possibly conspecific. Eastern American reports (ROSENBERG 2009; SALVADOR ET AL. 2014) still refer to *Ancistrobasis costulata* (Watson, 1879) as a distinct species.

DISCUSSION

Six species in Seguenziidae were found on the SASC, three of them reported as new to science in this study. Additional six seguenziids known from the NE Atlantic are *Basilissopsis vanheugteni* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017, *Seguenzia elegans* Jeffreys, 1885, *Seguenzia formosa* Jeffreys, 1876, *Carenzia carinata* (Jeffreys, 1877), *Quinnia ionica* (Watson, 1879) and *Ancistrobasis lavaleyei* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017.

The genus *Basilissopsis* shows a species-level radiation across the bathyal slopes off SW Europe and NW Africa, the Macaronesian and Azorean Islands, Lusitanian- and South Azorean Seamounts. *Basilissopsis vanheugteni* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017 is currently known from the Coral Patch Seamount only; *Basilissopsis athenae* n.sp. is known from the SASC and *Basilissopsis watsoni* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897 is widespread in the NE Atlantic.

Many species with a restricted distribution area have a paucispiral protoconch with less than one whorl, suggesting a direct development or a very short planktonic phase. Therefore, the expected restricted larval dispersal limits the ability for spreading over a large distribution area if deep-water barriers between islands or seamounts have to be crossed. All genera considered in this study have the typical larval shell of the Vetigastropoda, indicating a short, non-feeding planktonic stage (HADFIELD, STRATHMANN & STRATHMANN, 1997). It is yet unclear how one species in the genus *Basilissopsis* can spread

over a large area (*B. watsoni*) whereas other species are limited to smaller areas (*B. vanheugteni* and *B. athenae*). The three species in *Basilissopsis* are morphologically similar and probably have a common ancestor while the morphologically different *Basilissopsis rhyssa* and *Basilissopsis bassa* from the western Atlantic probably share a more distant ancestor.

Morphological radiations of endemic species within one genus in the NE Atlantic were also observed in for example *Clelandella* (GOFAS, 2005) which has the same kind of larval shell as the species considered here, and in the non-planktotrophic *Trituba* (GOFAS, 2003), *Manzonia*, *Gofasia* and *Porosalvania* (GOFAS, 2007), and others.

Endemic species in some genera in the NE Atlantic may be quite different from congeneric species elsewhere. *Carenzia marismontis* n. sp. is morphologically very different from the NE Atlantic *Carenzia carinata* and their common ancestor may be remote. An extreme case of a species with a likely ancient differentiation in the SASC is *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018. It is the only known Atlantic haloceratid with a reticulated sculpture and a protoconch indicating a non-planktonic development.

Endemics with a large dissimilarity within the genus as well as endemics with a similar morphology (forming a local radiation within the genus) give testimony to the unique evolution and biodiversity of the SASC. This circum-

stance stresses the need for protection of these areas for commercial exploitation to prevent destruction of the fragile habitats of these endemics.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BROMLEY R.G. 1981. Concepts in ichnotaxonomy illustrated by small round holes in shells. In: *Concept and method in Paleontology*. *Acta Geologica Hispanica*, 16 (1-2): 55-64.
- DAUTZENBERG P. 1889. *Contribution à la faune malacologique des Îles Açores. Résultats des Campagnes Scientifiques Accomplies sur son Yacht par Albert Ier Prince Souverain de Monaco*, I. Imprimerie de Monaco: Monaco. 112 pp. IV plates.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & DE BOURY E. 1897. *Campagnes Scientifiques de S.A. le Prince Albert Ier de Monaco. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse-Alice 1888-1896*. Mollusques appartenant à la famille des Scalidæ et au genre *Mathilda*. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 10: 62-74, pl. 2.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1896. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse Alice 1888-1895. 1. Mollusques Gastéropodes. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 9: 395-498, pls 15-22.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1897a. Campagnes scientifiques du Prince de Monaco. Diagnoses d'espèces nouvelles de Gastéropodes. *Bulletin de la Société Zoologique de France*, 22: 37-45.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1897b. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse Alice 1888-1896. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 10: 139-234, pls 3-7.
- DIJKSTRA H.H. & GOFAS S. 2004. Pectinoidea (Bivalvia: Propeamussiidae and Pectinidae) from some northeastern Atlantic seamounts. *Sarsia*, 89 (1): 33-78.
- FRANK N. 2018 *Short Cruise Report. M151. Atlantic Thermocline Ocean and Ecosystems Dynamic during Natural Climate Change. Ponta Delgada – Funchal, Portugal. October 6 – 31 October 2018*. 15 pp. (not published) Institut für Umweltpophysik, Universität Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany.
- GEIGER D.L. 2017. Four new Vetigastropoda (Anatomiadae, Seguenziidae) from the north-eastern Pacific. *Nautilus*, 131 (4): 226–232.
- GEIGER D.L. 2019. The family Seguenziidae Verrill, 1884 in the Northeast Pacific, including a comment on excessive numbers of taxonomic data portals. *Zoosymposia*, 13: 61-69.
- GEORGE K.H. 2010. *Abschlussbericht POS397*. (not published): 16 pp. DZMB, Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven, Germany.
- GOFAS S. 1993. *Mission océanographique SEAMOUNT 2. Compte rendu et liste des stations*. (not published): 1-30.
- GOFAS S. 2000. Four species of the family Fasciolaridae (Gastropoda) from the North Atlantic seamounts. *Journal of Conchology*, 37 (1): 7-16.
- GOFAS S. 2003. An endemic radiation of *Trituba* (Mollusca, Gastropoda) on the North Atlantic seamounts. *American Malacological Bulletin*, 17 (1-2): 45-63.
- GOFAS S. 2005. Geographical differentiation in *Clelandella* (Gastropoda: Trochidae) in the northeastern Atlantic. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 71: 133-144.
- GOFAS S. 2007. Rissoidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) from Northeast Atlantic seamounts. *Journal of Natural History*, 41 (13–16): 779–885.
- GOFAS S. 2018. A non-planktotrophic haloceratid (Gastropoda) from the Meteor Seamount group, central North Atlantic. *Iberus*, 36 (2): 149-155.
- GOFAS S. & BEU, A. 2003. Tonnoidean gastropods of the North Atlantic seamounts and the Azores. *American Malacological Bulletin*, 17 (1-2): 91-108.
- GOFAS S. & SALAS C. 2008. A review of European '*Mysella*' species (Bivalvia, Montacutiidae), with description of *Kurtiella* new genus. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 74 (2): 119-135.
- HADFIELD M.G., STRATHMANN M.F. & STRATHMANN R.R. 1997. Ciliary currents of non-feeding veligers in putative basal clades of gastropods. *Invertebrate Biology*, 116: 313–321.

- HOFFMAN L., VAN HEUGTEN B., LAVALEYE M.S.S. 2011. Gastropoda (Mollusca) from the Rockall and Hatton Banks, northeastern Atlantic Ocean. Part 2. *Miscellanea Malacologica*, 4 (6): 85-118.
- HOFFMAN L. & FREIWALD A. 2017. A unique and diverse amalgamated mollusk assemblage from the Coral Patch Seamount, eastern Atlantic. *Miscellanea Malacologica*, 7 (4): 61-79.
- HOUART R. 2001. *A review of the Recent Mediterranean and northeastern Atlantic species of Muricidae*. Evolver, Roma: 227 pp.
- JEFFREYS J.G. 1876. Preliminary report of the biological results of a cruise in H.M.S. Valorous to Davis Straits in 1875. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, 25: 177-237.
- JEFFREYS J.G. 1877. New and peculiar Mollusca of the Eulimidae and other families of Gastropoda, as well as of the Pteropoda, procured in the Valorous expedition. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, 19 (4): 317-339.
- JEFFREYS J.G. 1885. On the Mollusca procured during the H. M. S. "Lightning" and "Porcupine" expedition. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London*. Part 9: 27-63, pls 4-6.
- KRYLOVA E.M. 2006. *Bivalves of seamounts of the north-eastern Atlantic. Part 1*. In Mironov A.N., Gebruk A.V. & Southward A.J. (Eds): *Biogeography of the North Atlantic Seamounts*. KMK Scientific Press, Moscow. p. 76-95.
- LIMA S.F.B., CHRISTOFFERSEN M.L. & BARROS J.C.N. 2013. New Seguenziidae of the genus *Ancistrobasis* (Vetigastropoda: Seguenzioidea) from deep waters in the South Atlantic Ocean (Brazil). *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 54 (1): 103-108.
- LIMA S.F.B., CHRISTOFFERSEN M.L. & VILLACAMPA Y. 2014. Record of *Basilissopsis* for the bathyal region of the South Atlantic (Brazil) based on the description of a new species and the designation of a lectotype for *B. rhyssa* (Vetigastropoda, Trochidae). *Spixiana*, 37 (1): 27-34.
- MARSHALL B.A. 1983. Recent and Tertiary Seguenziidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) from the New Zealand region. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, 10: 235-262.
- MARSHALL B.A. 1988. New Seguenziidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) from the Tasman, South Pacific, and Southern Antilles Basins. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, 15: 235-247.
- MARSHALL B.A. 1991. Mollusca: Gastropoda: Seguenziidae from New Caledonia and the Loyalty Islands. In Crosnier A. & Bouchet P. (Eds.): *Résultats des campagnes Musorstom*, vol. 7. *Mémoires du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, 150: 41-109.
- OLIVERIO M. & GOFAS S. 2006. Coralliophiline diversity at mid-Atlantic seamounts (Neogastropoda, Muricidae, Coralliophilinae). *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 79 (1): 205-230.
- PEÑAS A. & ROLÁN E. 1999. Pyramidellidae (Gastropoda, Heterostropha) de la misión oceanográfica "Seamount 2". *Iberus suplemento 5*: 151-199.
- PHILIPPI R.A. 1844. *Enumeratio molluscorum Siciliae cum viventium tum in tellure tertiaria fossilium, quae in itinere suo observavit*. Vol. 2. Halle [Halis Saxorum]: Eduard Anton. iv + 303 pp., pls 13-28.
- POPPE G.T., TAGARO S.P. & DEKKER H. 2006. The Seguenziidae, Chilodontidae, Trochidae, Callostomatidae and Solariellidae of the Philippine Islands. *Visaya Supplement 2*: 1-228.
- QUINN J.F. 1983a. *Carenzia*, a new genus of Seguenziacea (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia) with the description of a new species from the northeastern Pacific. *Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington*, 96: 355-364.
- QUINN J.F. 1983b. A revision of the Seguenziacea Verrill, 1884 (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia). I. Summary and evaluation of the superfamily. *Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington*, 96 (4): 725-757.
- QUINN J.F. 1987. A revision of the Seguenziacea Verrill, 1884. II. The new genera *Hadroconus*, *Rotellenzia*, and *Asthelys*. *Nautilus*, 101 (2): 59-68.
- QUINN J.F. 1991. Systematic position of *Basilissopsis* and *Guttula*, and a discussion of the phylogeny of the Seguenzioidea (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia). *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 49 (1-2): 575-598.
- ROSENBERG G. 2009. *Malacolog 4.1.1: A Database of Western Atlantic Marine Mollusca*. [WWW database (version 4.1.1)] URL <http://www.malacolog.org/>.
- SALVADOR R.B., CAVALLARI D.C., SIMONE L.R.L. 2014. Seguenziidae (Gastropoda: Vetigastropoda) from SE Brazil collected by the Marion Dufresne (MD55) expedition. *Zootaxa*, 3878 (6): 536-550.
- WARÉN A. 1996. New and little known Mollusca from Iceland and Scandinavia. Part. 3. *Sarsia*, 81: 197-245.
- WATSON R.B. 1879. Mollusca of H.M.S. 'Challenger' Expedition. III. Trochidae, viz. the genera *Seguenzia*, *Basilissa*, *Gaza*, and *Bembix*. *Journal of the Linnean Society of London*, 14: 586-605.
- WATSON R.B. 1886. Report on the Scaphopoda and Gasteropoda collected by H.M.S. Challenger during the years 1873-76. Report on the Scientific Results of the Voyage of H.M.S. Challenger during the years 1873-76. *Zoology*, 15 (part 42): 1-756, pls 1-50.
- WISSHAK M., KROH A., BERTLING M., KNAUST D., NIELSEN J.K., JAGT J.W.M., NEUMANN C., NIELSEN K.S.S. 2015. In defence of an iconic ichnogenus *Oichnus* Bromley, 1981. *Annales Societatis, Geologorum Poloniae*, 85: 445-451.